

Classification of Natural, Accidental and Artificial Body Marks using Machine Learning Techniques

Dr. Dayanand G Savakar¹, Danesh Telsang^{2*}, Dr. Anil Kannur³

¹Department of Computer Science, Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, Karnataka, India

^{2*}Research Scholar, Department of Computer Science, Rani Channamma University, Belagavi, Karnataka, India

³Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Nagarjuna College of Engineering and Technology, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India-562164

Abstract

Digital image forensics is used in various applications, with person search and identification, in which accused, victims, desired or missing persons, or even unidentified bodies, or even general scenes, must be regarded visually. When only uncontrolled, unprofessionally generated photographs are available during an inquiry, the traditional matching method may be impractical. Moles, scars and tattoos are all examples of dermatological features that can describe subjects in an image. This article proposes a system for classifying and identifying dermatological characteristics such as moles, scars, and tattoos based on machine learning methods. As a second part, we carry out a comparative analysis on existing classifiers and suggest the best machine learning classifier for the classification of dermatological features. The system mainly includes segmentation module performed using Region-based Active contour method, Feature Extraction Module includes extraction of texture, shape and color features and Classification is carried out by Artificial Neural Network and Cubic- SVM classifier. As a result, the Cubic SVM classifier has resulted to be the best suitable classifier with 91.5% of accuracy.

Keywords-Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Cubic- SVM classifier, Region-based Active, Mole, Scar, Tattoo.

1. INTRODUCTION

We have experienced globally a revolution of digitization during the last decade of the twentieth century. As a result, the majority of our valuable data will be housed digitally. The rise of the necessity to update and enforce laws is also changing in this age of information technology [01]. This makes traditional crimes, particularly those involving banking and business, are continually changing as a result of technology improvements. Computer systems and digital equipment have grown in importance to determine facts in a growing number of researches [02]. This is where digital forensics comes into play, addressing law enforcement's well-defined requirements for

optimizing the use of this rapidly expanding middle of electronic signal, where machine learning will perform a serious role through automating time-consuming operations. [03].

Digital forensics is a subfield of forensic science disturbed with recovering and examining digital data [04]. It is a rapidly growing field that is constantly striving to keep up with technological advancements and their implementation to recognize, preserve, analyse, and restore data from computer systems & other digital storage. "Big digital forensic evidence" [05] is today's most difficult problems for law enforcement agencies.

Identification is the process of determining a person's individuality in forensics. Authentication of the living/dead person or skull bone remains seems to be the most significant aspect for resolving any case for a leading investigator. Congenital and acquired body marks are two other characteristics that can help with forensic identification. Congenital marks have been present since birth, such as birthmarks, moles, and congenital abnormalities. Acquired, on the other hand, are those that appear on the body after birth. Tattoos, professional marks, scars, body abnormalities, and body piercing are examples of such body marks [06]. In this paper, we have used image processing methods and machine learning techniques to segment and classify three types of body marks such as natural, accidental, and artificial which include moles, scars, and tattoos.

Scars are formed as a result of tissue regeneration via fibrosis and cicatrisation [07]. All scars are eternal in their anatomical and morphological implications. Scars might alter in volume as people grow older, but their patterns remain the same during their lives. Permanent scars on the skin and the injury induced by wounds (cuts, accidents, or surgery) could be used to prove identity. The shape, size, age, and category of a scar expose a great deal around the kind, time, and weapon used to inflict the harm." In addition, "occupational marks are features that result from work adaptation," [08]. "Work-related marks are traits that develop as a result of workplace adaptation. It denotes a person's identity and social status, whether alive or dead." Tattoo marks, which are formed through instilling dyes of various colours into the skin via a variety of puncture techniques; body needle pricks, especially in men; and unexpected malformations in the event of amputation, paralysis, or loss of vision are all important features of proof of identification in digital forensics.

This study Proposes, an automated system for the classification of three types of body acquired images as natural, accidental, and artificial images which includes mole, scar and tattoo. The main aim is to classify the body marks and to verify the best machine learning technique suitable for the classification. The system is made up of different modules: Pre-Processing: where we eliminate unwanted noise, hair and resize the images. Secondly segmentation: to obtain the area of attention in the input images we are adopting a region-based active contour method. Feature extraction and classification: for discrimination between these three types of images we are

combining three types of features for example, colour, texture, and shape features are extracted and trained using classifiers.

The following is how the paper is organised: Section 2 contains a survey report on various methods. The research problem is defined in Section 3. The methodology used to develop the projected method is discussed in Section 4. Section 5 presents the outcomes and comparative study. Lastly, Section 6 achieves the paper by outlining the future scope of the research.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Mariam A. Sheha et al. [2012] developed a computerized method for melanoma diagnosis that uses dermoscopy images to differentiate between Melanocytic Nevi and Malignant Melanoma. Pre-processing, feature extraction using the grey level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM), feature selection, classification using a multilayer perceptron classifier (MLP), and assessment are the processes in the technique. The system enables texture analysis without requiring the user to select and identify an object of interest. Segmentation was thus avoided. The results indicated that texture analysis is an effective method for discriminating melanocytic skin tumours with a high degree of accuracy of 92 per cent.

Farzam Kharaji Nezhadian et al. [2017] developed an algorithm for separating malignant and benign dermoscopic images. The system uses the active counter model for segmentation, and the user ascertained the initial district to improve accuracy. Two characteristics were extracted: texture and colourful elements. The most efficient feature was chosen to be the TC features for wavelet transform estimation matrices. They proved that texture-based features were the first in this field to diagnose disease, with a 97 % accuracy rate when used with a support vector machine classifier.

Unsang Park et al. [2010] devised a technique for detecting facial features such as scars, moles, and freckles in order to improve face image matching and recovery performance. Main facial features such as the eyes, nose, and mouth are placed using the active appearance model. Second, we identify Laplacian-of-Gaussian blobs & morphological operators. Finally, experiments on the FERET database and 2 mugshot databases from the forensic domain demonstrate that incorporating soft biometric traits greatly improves a cutting-edge commercial matcher's face recognition performance.

Jung-Eun Lee et al. [2008] suggested a framework for matching & retrieving tattoo images that is content-based (CBIR). We want to fetch all tattoo images in the database that are similar looking to a question tattoo image. The feature-based similarity among the inquiry tattoo image & tattoos in the criminal database is calculated using SIFT features extracted from tattoo images & possibly linked demographic data.

Shiksha Singh et.al. [2020] have developed a breast cancer detection and classification system using histopathology-based features. They converted RGB images to grayscale as a pre-processing step and then extracted GLCM, LTE, LBP, and HTF features from grayscale images. After that, the gathering of these features is combined to form a feature vector for classification. Classification is performed using the cubic SVM machine learning algorithm in conjunction with the k-fold cross-validation method. They conducted tests on publicly available datasets and obtained an accuracy of 92.3 per cent using a cubic SVM classifier.

The function of textural traits in the detection of skin cancer was investigated by **Xiaoqing Yuan et al. [2006]**. A 3-layer mechanism integrated into the support vector machine (SVM) technology is utilised to enhance simplification error rate & processing proficiency. I texture feature extraction, which includes statistical, model-based & filtering-based techniques, with multi-channel filtering being the most successful and precise, and (ii) texture analysis and classification, which includes neural networks, decision trees & support vector machines. The algorithm's performance is determined by evaluating it to a collection of benchmark texture images, then twenty-two pairs of genuine clinical skin lesion photographs. A fourth-order polynomial kernel, according to their research, can reliably predict the malignancy of any pixel inside a given skin lesion image by 70%.

Brian Heflin and colleagues [2012] developed a novel technique for detection and categorising scars, marks, and tattoos. They are primarily composed of an automatic variant of the GrabCut for segmentation in conjunction with a method for detecting tattoos on the face. The detection elements have been tuned specifically for the purpose of identifying candidate regions that may comprise an intriguing dermatological feature. The open set classification method is used to account for the "unknown" class of objects and to eliminate those that are not scars, marks, or tattoos, as well as to facilitate the identification of specific tattoo classifications.

Scott T. Acton et al. [2008] used image analysis to create a tool for pairing tattoos and fetching similar tattoos from a tattoo database. The researchers present a novel active contour CBIR method based on local features containing global colour and edge orientation information. By merging edge-based features into a single scale and colour incidence statistics, the global features advancing feature-based matching methods. For texture analysis, Haar wavelet decomposition is used; for colour representation, hue-saturation-value histograms are being used & for shape characterization, Fourier shape descriptors are used. Finally, the technique based on global image features is defined.

Huang Yi et al. [2015] investigated the effect of non-tattoo areas on the performance of image-based recognition systems. Cropped tattoo images with the most of the useless data deleted are known as segmented tattoo images. Their system employs SIFT and SURF matching techniques, and four different settings are available: both probe and gallery set with segmentation, both probe and gallery set without segmentation, probe set with segmentation and gallery set without

segmentation, and vice versa. They have demonstrated that non-tattoo regions impair matching performance, implying that tattoo matching will benefit from precise tattoo identification.

3. METHODOLOGY

The proposed classification of natural, accidental, and artificial body marks systems includes image acquisition, segmentation, feature extraction & training the classifier. The system automatically classifies the mole, scar, and tattoo images. The steps of the developed system are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: This diagram depicts the proposed system's architecture.

3.1 Image Acquisition

The classification system begins with the acquisition of an image of a mole, scar, or tattoo as an input image. This image was captured using a Canon 1300D digital camera equipped with a 1.5X to 10X lens zoom capability, and a few additional images were gathered from online sources. A database is created with three classes mole, scar, and tattoo where each class includes 150 images and a total of 450 images. Figure2 shows the details of the database.

Figure2: (a)Mole (b) Scar (c) Tattoo

3.2 Pre-processing

Pre-processing is a process that involves a series of operations on the input images. It essentially enhances the image, making it segmentation-ready. To begin, some images of moles, scars, and

tattoos contain artefacts, primarily hair; these artefacts can cause the segmentation algorithm to malfunction. The DullRazormethod [18], a pre-processing method for removing artefacts, works well with hair and other artefacts in our database images. As illustrated in Figure 3(c), the outcomes are strikingly similar to those obtained using the median filter. Secondly, the image RESIZE method is applied to resize all the images present in the database to the same size.

Thirdly, any unwanted data added to the image during transmission via digital media is referred to as noise. We used spatial filtering to eliminate noise in this work. The term "spatial filtering" refers to filtering functions conducted directly on the pixels of an image. Moving the filter mask around an image is all that is required.

Figure 3: Hair removal through the DullRazormethod: (a) novel image, (b) mask hairs, (c) After hair removal image

3.3 Segmentation using Region-based Active contour

Kass et al. introduced the active contour model, dubbed "Snake," in 1988 [19]. The basic idea behind inactive contour models is to develop a dynamic curve toward the limits of objects in an image, subject to certain limitations. Since the seminal work of [19][20][21], active contour models have been demonstrated to be highly efficient. Segmentation techniques based on active contour models describe an energy functional on an active curve lowered when the curve conforms to the object's border. As an outcome, the image segmentation issue is converted into an energy functional decrease issue, which can be conveyed mathematically as an optimization issue with the curve separating regions assisting as the optimization variable. It starts by drawing rough boundary lines around regions/objects of interest and then fine-tuning them until they match their real boundary lines. Figure 4 depicts the outcomes of the segmentation technique employed to each category of images.

Figure 4: Outcomes of Segmentation (a) Mole Segmentation (b) Scar Segmentation (c) Tattoo Segmentation.

3.4 Feature Extraction

The term "Feature Extraction" refers to the process of extracting unique features from an image that best represent it. Certain characteristics, such as shape, colour, and texture, aid in classifying the image as a mole, scar, and tattoo. We can distinguish natural, accidental, and artificial body marks by extracting and training a classifier on these features. To extract features from images, we have used 18 color features, 6 shape features, and 4 texture features from the classes of database i.e., mole, scar, and tattoo. This section gives a detailed description of different features extraction methods used in this work. We worked on a total of 450 images out of which 150 were mole, 150 scar, and 150 tattoo images.

3.4.1 Color Feature Extraction

RGB is the intuitive choice to extract features when we require color information of the object. In this work, we are using mean, range, and variance from each color channel. These values are put into a vector and are used to train the classifier. Usually mole, scar, and tattoo are found in red, blue, and green. To classify these images, we are extracting 18 forms of color features as shown in Table 1 below for all three types of images.

Table 1: Color Features list

Red Mean	Red Variance	Red Range
Green Mean	Green Variance	Green Range
Blue Mean	Blue Variance	Blue Range
Hue Mean	Hue Variance	Hue Range
Saturation Mean	Saturation Variance	Saturation Range
Value Mean	Value Variance	Value Range

The procedure to extract these color features is done by breaking up the image into the components of Red, Green, and Blue [22]. The Red, Green, and blue colour element values of natural, accidental, and artificial body mark images are normalised to have values in the range [0,1][29].

3.4.2 Shape Feature Extraction

Shape representations can define shapes by determining the degree of similarity between shapes represented by their geometric features [23]. These are typically used as filters to remove irrelevant matches or in conjunction with other shape descriptors to discriminate between shapes. From each mole, scar, and tattoo classes images we have extracted five shape parameters such as are Eccentricity, Area, Equivdiameter, Convexity, and Solidity [29].

3.4.3 Texture Feature Extraction

The Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) and associated texture feature calculations are image analysis tools [24]. The GLCM is a table that shows how frequently various sets of grey levels co-occur in an image or segment given an image made up of pixels, each with an intensity value. The parts of the GLCM are used in texture feature computation to provide an indicator of the intensity variation at the pixel of interest. We extracted four GLCM features from all of the images of the class mole, scar, and tattoo [29].

3.5 Classifiers

The goal of this research was to assess multiple kinds of classifiers in order to determine which ones are most useful at categorising mole, scar, and tattoo images using shape, colour, and texture features. The two classifiers evaluated including the ANN and Cubic SVM which are explained in this section.

3.5.1 Artificial Neural Network

There are three different types for three types of body marks: mole, scar, and tattoo. The texture, colour, and shape of the body mark will be used as inputs to a neural network, and the kind of body mark will be used as a goal. Specified an input comprising the 28 features, the neural system is required to accurately classify the type of body mark. This is accomplished by feeding previously recorded inputs into a neural network and instructing it to yield the required outputs [13]. This is known as neural network training. Initially, data is prepared to create two sets of training and testing set using all the three types of features together colour, shape, and texture features are extracted. The classes for Mole, Scar, and Tattoo are represented as [1 0 0], [0 1 0], and [0 0 1], and Network selects randomly training and testing data.

Test images are captured in the same manner as training images. Precautions are taken during the image capture process. The image should be distinct from the one used for training. Testing data can be derived from a subset of the training data.

The following step is to guide a neural network to recognise the classes. Due to the random weights used to train the neural network, the outcomes vary slightly among runs. To protect this random nature, the random seed or twister is set. 28 neurons are used to construct the hidden layer of a feed-forward network with ten hidden layers. As an outcome, the network is training-ready. Now that the network is ready to be trained using a scale conjugate gradient, it can be used to train it. Training will proceed indefinitely as long as the network enhances on the validation set. The test set calculates classification accuracy using a confusion matrix to provide an objective, network-independent measure of network exactness. When the network response is compared to the respective target response, a classification matrix detailing the classifier's performance is generated.

3.5.2 Cubic SVM

SVM is a supervised machine learning method that may be used to help with data classification and regression. The SVM divides the data into two kinds by plotting it on a hyperplane. To produce the geometrical hyperplane, SVM uses a mathematical function recognized as the kernel. Polynomial, linear, non-linear sigmoid and radial basis (RBF) functions are examples of kernel functions [25]. The kernel is explained as follows:

$$k(x') = \int \begin{matrix} 1 & \text{if } |x'| \leq 1 \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise} \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

The internal item of 2 adjacent points in feature space with an advantageous feature is computed by these functions. As an outcome, it describes a familiarity concept in a low-cost, high-dimensional space. The suggested technique employs a polynomial kernel function of order 3, as shown in the equation under:

$$k(x_i, x_j) = (x_i^T \cdot x_j + 1)^d \quad (2)$$

Where d is the degree of polynomial Cubic Kernel Function:

$$k(x_i, x_j) = (x_i^T \cdot x_j + 1)^3 \quad (3)$$

There are 28 features extracted from the segmented body marks from each class of mole, scar and tattoo. To discriminate between these three distinct trends, the learning algorithm employs a decision function; the learning algorithm automatically determines the optimal decision function from the current information. The SVM is fed the optimal feature vector of colour, shape, and texture extracted from a mole, scar, and tattoo. The SVM is trained using feature vectors, and the

result of the training is a boundary defined by these data. When new data is received, the decision function determines which classification the data belongs to.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

All trials are conducted in MATLAB, and the approach is assessed using 450 photos, 150 of which contain mole images, 150 of which include scar images, and 150 of which have tattoo images. This section describes the experimental setup for the ANN and Cubic SVM classifiers. It presents the results in a confusion matrix, true and false predictions values, and the suggested technique's overall accuracy.

4.1 ANN Classifier

Collecting samples of moles, scars, and tattoos is part of the job. Following image segmentation, the dataset is prepared for training the neural network. Twenty-eight input layers, ten hidden levels, and three output layers are set to explore. After that, the dataset is aimlessly partitioned into training and testing subsets. The architecture of the ANN classifier is depicted in Figure 5. Additionally, it is divided into three categories: mole, scar, and tattoo.

Figure 5: Architecture of ANN Classifier.

Work entails the accuracy of the constructed neural network classifier is quantified. This word refers to a model's ability to accurately forecast a class of data. Classification accuracy is determined through the percentage of correctly classified test sets. The confusion matrix and the receiver operator character trait curve were used to determine the neural network's performance (ROC). Random data segment, Scaled Conjugate Gradient for training, Cross-Entropy for performance& 55 iterations comprise the platform.is amassing samples of moles, scars, and tattoos on the body. Following image segmentation, the dataset is prepared for training the neural network. Twenty-eight input layers, ten hidden levels, and three output layers are set to explore. After that, the dataset is aimlessly partitioned into training and testing subsets. The architecture of the ANN classifier is depicted in Figure 5. Additionally, it is divided into three categories: mole, scar, and tattoo.

The experiment is valued for a total of 450 images which includes every 150 images of mole, scar, and tattoo. The performance of the proposed classification system has achieved is 90.0% of accuracy with a 10.0% failure rate out of 450 images. Each class-wise prediction is tabulated in Table 2. Results of the training data show that tattoo class has the highest accuracy of 90%,

Table 2: Prediction values of each class using ANN Classifier

Class	True Prediction Value	False Prediction Value
Mole	85.3%	14.7%
Scar	88.7%	11.3%
Tattoo	96.0%	4.0%

The diagonal cells represent the number of successfully classified classes, while the off-diagonal cells represent misclassified cases. The percentage of properly classified cases (in green)& the percentage of incorrectly classified cases (in red) are displayed in the blue cell on the bottom right [26]. Figure 6 demonstrate the confusion matrix for each class as well as the overall accuracy of the proposed technique.

The receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves for the 2 output classes are represented by the bright lines in this graph. As the threshold is raised, the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve displays the real positive rate (sensitivity) versus the false positive rate (specificity). An ideal trial would display points in the upper-left corner and have 100 percent sensitivity and specificity [26]. The true positive rate is compared to the false positive rate using the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve (1-specificity). The curves are positioned among the diagonal and the upper-left corner, but mostly toward the upper-left corner, as shown in Figure 7. This network's ROC plot indicates a high degree of categorization across the three categories, as shown in Figure 7. The curves in all ROC graphs show that the suggested technique's performance, as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6: Target class confusion matrix among class1 mole, class2 scar and class3 tattoo.

Figure 7: Best validation performance of ANN

Figure 8: ANN Classifier accuracies for the selection of various mole, scar, and tattoo classes

4.2 Cubic SVM Classifier

The cubic SVM is broken into two parts: training and testing. It is trained and evaluated using body mark datasets and a randomly generated dataset. The experiment used 450 sample images, 150 of which were of moles, 150 of which were of scars, and 150 of which were of tattoos. In the first step, the features file is given a module in that each image contains 28 features. The cross-validation folds are set to 10 folds. Figure 8. Represents the results of the proposed method using cubic SVM Classifier.

The confusion matrix plots to know how the currently designated classifier achieved in each class. The cubic SVM classifier was able to show a more correct classification of all the three classes than the wrong classification. Figure 9.a. shows the number of observations in which 125 moles, 118 scars, and 131 tattoo images are correctly recognised, and 24, 32, and 19 are incorrectly labelled. The confusion matrix is depicted in Figure 9. b, and its specifics are included in the following table 3. The suggested technique has an overall accuracy of 91.5 per cent true and 8.5 per cent false out of 450 samples. The true positive rate is depicted in Figure 9. c, as is the false-negative rate.

Table 3: Prediction Values of Each Class using Cubic SVM Classifier

Class	True Prediction Value	False Prediction Value
Mole	78%	22%
Scar	86%	14%
Tattoo	87%	13%

Figure9: Confusion Matrix of Cubic SVM Results (a) Confusion Matrix, (b) No.ofObservation, (c) Positive predictive values false discovery rates

In Figure 10.a. the area below the curve (AUC) shows the number of the total possible thresholds of the classifier which is equal to 0.87. The AUC of the Quadratic SVM is equal to 0.90 which means that it has a better performance compared to other classifiers.

Figure 10.b. shows the parallel coordinates plot of the Cubic SVM. The parallel coordinates plot shows the useful variables or features of the mole, scar, and tattoo that contributed to their discrimination. A parallel axis represents the data dimension. A data point corresponds to a polyline intersecting the vertical axes at the position corresponding to the data class value.

Figure 10: Plots of Cubic SVM Classifier (a) ROC (b) Proposed method parallel coordinates plots.

4.3 Comparative analysis

The experiment is conducted using a 450-image collection of natural, accidental, and artificial body markings. The proposed techniques' results will be compared to those of other current approaches. The comparison is made in terms of classifier types, not body markers, due to the novelty of the presented method. The findings are compared using the method's accuracy, which is detailed in Table 4.

Table 4: Comparison between the classifiers

Sl.No	Classifier	Results
1	SVM [18]	92.1%
2	Multiple-Instance SVM [19]	92.1%
3.	Neural Network with backpropagation [14]	75%
4.	Neural Network with backpropagation [17]	75.6%
5.	Auto-associative neural network [18]	80.8%
6.	Auto- associative neural network [19]	82.6%
7.	Proposed method using ANN	90.0%
8.	Proposed method using Cubic SVM	91.5%

The proposed method using Cubic SVM classifier has given recovering outcomes as compared with the other approaches.

5. CONCLUSION

We've created a classification system for images of moles, scars, and tattoos. With the rising use of natural, accidental and artificial body marks in forensics and law enforcement for victim and suspicious identification, such a structure will be critical in detaining suspects and recognizing victims. The system's primary objective is to correctly classify all three types of images and to recommend the best classifier for classification. For Segmentation, we have used the region-based active contour method and obtained the most accurate segmentation on tattoo images. For classification purposes, we have used two types of classifiers cubic SVM and ANN and to calculate the best classifier method for the classification of body marks we have compared with existing methods based on classifiers. As we are working on a smaller database Cubic SVM classifier has resulted to be the best accurate classifier when compared with ANN Classifier.

Reference

- [1] Bell DE, LaPadula LJ (1973). Secure computer systems: Mathematical foundations. Mitre Corp Bedford MA. Link: <https://bit.ly/3fPT1rR>
- [2] Denning DE (1987). An intrusion-detection model. *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering* 222-232.

- [3] Perdisci R, Lee W, Feamster N (2010). Behavioral clustering of http-based malware and signature generation using malicious network traces.
- [4] Monika Kulshreshtha , P.R. Mondal,(2017). “Acquired body marks: A mode of identification in Forensics”, *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine* 52,.
- [5] Hilmand Khan, SarmadHanif and Bakht Muhammad,(2021). “A survey of machine learning applications in digital forensics”, Department of Computer Science, CIIT,.
- [6] Modi NJ. Modi's(1977). Textbook of Medical Jurisprudence and Toxicology. Bombay: Tripathipvt. limited;
- [7] Parikh CK. Parikh's(2007). Textbook of Medical Jurisprudence and Toxicology. CBS Publisher and distributions;
- [8] Beale M, Hagan M, Demuth H(2013). *Neural Network Toolbox User's Guide*. MATLAB, The MathWorks,;
- [9] Mariam A.Sheha, Mai S.Mabrouk, AmrSharawy,(2012). “Automatic Detection of Melanoma Skin Cancer using Texture Analysis”, *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975 – 8887) Volume 42– No.20,.
- [10] FarzamKharajiNezhadian, SaeidRashidi,(2017). “Melanoma skin cancer detection using color and new texture features”, *Artificial Intelligence and Signal Processing (AISP)*,.
- [11] Unsang Park and Anil K. Jain,(2010).” Face Matching and Retrieval Using Soft Biometrics”, *IEEE, Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, Vol. 5, No. 3, September.
- [12] Jung-Eun Lee, Anil K. Jain and Rong Jin,(2008). “Scars, Marks and Tattoos (Smt): Soft Biometric For Suspect And Victim Identification”, *IEEE*.
- [13] Shiksha Singh, Rajesh Kumar,(2020). “Histopathological Image Analysis for Breast Cancer Detection Using Cubic SVM”, *7th International Conference on Signal Processing and Integrated Networks (SPIN)*, *IEEE*,.
- [14] XiaojingYuan,Zhenyu Yang, George ZouridakisandNizarMullani,(2006). “SVM-based Texture Classification and Application to Early Melanoma Detection”, *Proceedings of the 28th IEEE EMBS Annual International Conference New York City, USA*.
- [15] Brian Heflin, Walter Scheirer, T.E. Boult(2012):“Detecting and Classifying Scars, Marks, and Tattoos Found in the Wild”, *IEEE*,.
- [16] Scott T. Acton , Adam Rossi,(2008). “Matching and Retrieval of Tattoo Images: Active Contour Cbir And Glocal Image Features”, *IEEE*,.
- [17] Huang Yi, Peicong Yu, XingpengXu, and Adams Wai Kin Kong,(2015). “The Impact of Tattoo Segmentation on the Performance of Tattoo Matching”, *IEEE International WIE Conference on Electrical and Computer Engineering*, 19-20, Dec.
- [18] Lee T, Ng V, Gallagher R, Coldman A, McLean D (1997) Dullrazor A software approach to hair removal from images. *ComputBiol Med* 27(6):533–543 .
- [19] M. Kass, A. Witkin and D. Terzopoulos,(1988) “Snakes: Active Contour Models,” *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 1(4): 321-331,.
- [20] C. Xu and J. L. Prince,(1997). “Gradient Vector Flow: A New External Force for Snakes,” *IEEE Proceedings on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, 66-71,.
- [21] C. Xu, J. L. Prince. Snakes,(1998). “Shapes and Gradient Vector Flow,” *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, 359-369,.
- [22] T. Kapur, W. E. L. Grimson and R. Kikinis,(1995). “Segmentation of Brain Tissue MR Images,” *First Conference on Computer Vision, Virtual Reality and Robotics in Medicine*,.
- [23] R.VenkataRamanaChary1 ,Dr.D.Rajya Lakshmi2 and Dr. K.V.N Sunit,(2012). “Feature Extraction Methods For Color Image Similarity”, *Advanced Computing: An International Journal (ACIJ)*, Vol.3, No.2, March.
- [24] Yang Mingqiang , KpalmaKidiyo , Ronsin Joseph, “A survey of shape feature extraction techniques”,
- [25] D. A. Clausi,(2002).“An analysis of co-occurrence texture statistics as a function of grey level quantization,” *Canadian Journal of remote sensing*, vol. 28, pp. 45-62,.
- [26] SVM Cubic Kernel Functions-Introduction to SVM Kernel & Examples,” *Dataflair*. .
- [27] R. Gonzalez and R. Woods,(2002) *Digital image processing*..

- [28] A. K. Jaiswal and R. Srivastava,(2019). “Copy Move Forgery Detection Using Shift Invariant SWT and Block Division Mean Features,” in *Recent Trends in Communication, Computing, and Electronics*, , pp. 289–299.
- [29] Savakar, D. G., Telsang, D., & Kannur, A. (2021). Artificial neural network for identification and classification of natural body marks. In *International Conference on Communication, Computing and Electronics Systems* (pp. 541-555). Springer, Singapore.